

“CORRUPTION”-A PROBLEM TO BUILD AN ENLIGHTENED SOCIETY

Mahammadaliyeva Naima Akramjon qizi

Teacher of the 1-vocational college of Chortok district

“Corruption-development obstacle. Never with corruption
we can't achieve our goal”

Sh. Mirziyoyev

ABSTRACT

“Enlightened society” is built by intellectuals. Intellectuals are prepared by the higher education system. Today, there is a problem of “Corruption” in legal societies. This vice is a chain of evils, a prelude to negative ways, and it is a dangerous criminal that threatens security. The fight against corruption is the guarantee of the safety of the state and society, and the community will progress, this vice undermines the foundations of democracy and security stability, directly affects the functioning of markets, degrades quality and threatens the safety of people, criminal liability, terrorism and other phenomena to visit the roots creates conditions. This vice did not become yesterday or today. About this, Abu Nasr Farabi, one of our scholars, noted in his work “The City of Virtuous People” that “one of the immediate problems in building a civil society is corruption.” Therefore, the fight against this disease should be comprehensive.

Looking at the history of the world, we can see that religious sources have a special attitude towards this disease. This is stated in the holy book of Islam. Allah the Almighty says in the Holy Qur'an: "Do not eat your wealth among yourselves in unjust and impure ways!" (That is, do not eat each other's rights!) And do not give (bribe your property) to the governors, knowing (that you are committing a sin), to eat a part of people's wealth in sinful - impure ways! (Surat al-Baqara, verse 188). In other words, if it is said that you should not bribe governors so that they will appropriate the rights of others to you, it is mentioned in the narration of Imam at Termizi, Ibn Hibban, Hokim. Abu Huraira, may God be pleased with him, says: "The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, cursed both the bribe-giver and the bribe-taker." In another tradition, it is said: "And the person in the middle." Today, corruption, which is an evil that hinders the development of the state, is strictly responsible for both the receiver and the giver. If we look at Tabarani's narration in history, Umm Salama, may God bless him and grant him peace, narrates: "The

Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, said: "May God curse both the bribe-giver and the bribe-taker in any ruling." we can see that it is also strongly condemned. The Bible says, "Do not accept gifts, because a gift makes the blind see and changes the truth." From this we can see that regardless of which religion he is a representative of, we can know that the emergence and promotion of this evil in society is strongly condemned.

Nowadays, it should be noted that this disease is a factor that threatens the development of all countries, regardless of whether they are big or small, rich or poor.

In recent years, large-scale reforms aimed at putting an end to the factors of corruption in all spheres of state and society construction have been consistently implemented in our country to prevent and fight against it. In particular, the program of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 3, 2021 regarding the implementation of the "Strategy of Actions" on the 5 priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Youth Support and Population Health Promotion" in the course of the ongoing reforms. In order to ensure the implementation of Clause 34 of the Annex to Decree No. PF-6155 (Further improvement of the anti-corruption system), the project of the National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the fight against corruption for 2021-2025 was developed. Also, the decree of the President of July 6, 2021 No. 6757 mentions the drastic reduction of corruption factors. We can say that the measures taken are of great importance for national development and the future of the country.

Currently, each country is developing a separate measure to combat this disease.

Today, each state and society chooses its own way to fight against corruption, more precisely, its effectiveness is determined by the results of the actions taken. According to the information given at the briefing held on August 19, 2021 with the participation of Durдона Ochilova, head of the information service of the Anti-Corruption Agency, in the course of extensive reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan, 34 criminal cases related to corruption were initiated within one year, of which 26 were related to looting of budget funds. if there are, 2 are the crimes of fraud and bribery by fraud. As stated in Article 210 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, such corruption crimes are punishable by a fine of 50 to 100 times the minimum monthly salary or imprisonment for up to 5 years with deprivation of certain rights. When this crime is committed in aggravating circumstances, a penalty of imprisonment from 10 to 15 years is imposed.

Today, in our republic, measures are being taken to determine the causes of crime, and exposed corrupt officials are severely punished. Crime within the country is always strictly controlled by the state. A number of long-term measures have been implemented in order to prevent crime from spreading and corrupt officials to be free.

They define our crime-fighting strategy. It has already been proven how much more reasonable it is to introduce preventive measures, such as preventing crime, rather than punishing it. After all, in Article 2 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is not for nothing that crime prevention is defined as one of the main tasks of the criminal law. Today, life itself shows that the goals of the fight against corruption cannot be achieved only by criminal-legal means. We think that not only the state bodies, but also the society and all our citizens are responsible for the fight against such moral disorder. Therefore, the joint action of the state and society, as well as non-governmental non-profit organizations, is considered the best way to achieve effective results. The fight against corruption remains one of the most urgent issues of today's world. The fight against this disease covers many countries of the world. The Republic of Uzbekistan also contributes to the fight against corruption. Currently, a number of programs have been adopted in the framework of the fight against corruption in our republic, and extensive work is being carried out on them. As part of the fight against corruption, the Ministry of Justice has developed a plan of measures, in which the agencies and institutions of the justice system are actively participating. In particular, a number of anti-corruption activities have been carried out in the training center for lawyers under the Ministry of Justice, and a number of anti-corruption activities are being carried out in higher education institutions under the Ministry of Justice. In addition, in the 2018-2019 academic year, a monograph on "The International Standards System Regulating Liability of Legal Entities for Corruption Offenses" by Associate Professor G. Alimov, Associate Professor B. Israilov (team of authors) was published. by in December 2018 in co-authorship with scientists of Saint-Petersburg Polytechnic University "Sovremennaya sistema protivodeystviya otmyvaniyu prestupnyx dokhodov i finansirovaniyu terrorisma" and "Ekonomicheskaya bezopasnost" training manuals, under the grant of Science and Technology Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Ministry of Innovative Development) G. Alimov and B. A monograph entitled "Tenevaya ekonomika, korrupcion, vzyatochnichestva: ugolovno-proavovaya otsenka" was prepared and published under the co-authorship of Israilov.

Also, for all groups of listeners who regularly come to study at the Center for the Advancement of Lawyers, the center organizes "Legal foundations of the fight against corruption in Uzbekistan" by the Department of Criminal Legal Sciences, "International legal foundations of the fight against corruption and the experience of foreign countries" by the Department of International Law and Human Rights." lectures are being given. Large-scale work is being carried out to fundamentally improve the education system of our country, increase its quality and efficiency, and strengthen the material and technical base of educational institutions. At the same time,

efforts have been made to ensure the transparency of admission processes to higher educational institutions, and to prevent corruption and bribery in education. However, despite the comprehensive measures taken to fight against bribery, there are still fraudsters who say "I will admit you to study, I will solve the test" and want to earn a lot of money. Unfortunately, there are not many parents who act like "My child can get a diploma, it's just a matter of course" and consider whether their child's abilities, knowledge and potential are sufficient or not, as a secondary issue. Frankly, these cases have been the sore point of corruption in the education system for years. Due to the reforms in the field, the situation has changed radically, and the principle that those who have the knowledge, ability, and potential should study began to be followed. That's why now they are trying hard to root out corruption in education. The first step in this regard began with the regulation of the process of passing tests. In short, all conditions and opportunities are being created for the applicants, starting from the document acceptance to the process of conducting the test exams. The main thing is to follow the principle of honesty and openness. But even though the fight against corruption is becoming more and more strict, it seems that its roots are still preserved. The healthy environment in our society is still being encountered by some impure people, who have made a habit of living on dirty food, neglecting the interests of young people who have diligently received education and sent them to study with various dreams. Especially on the eve of the beginning of the new academic year, there is a saying that such a harsh practice is starting to become more serious. It is a pity that such a situation is visible not only in higher education institutions, but also in lyceums and colleges, even in comprehensive schools. In order to eliminate corruption in education, the first task is to increase the legal culture of people's minds, students, parents, teachers and school administration, to destroy and destroy their old views, hardened stereotypes, complexes.

Because as long as there is a tendency to bribery, evil is committed secretly. First of all, it is necessary to form the first worldview about corruption, its harms and consequences from a young age, and create an idea about the simplest forms of bribery in children. As important as awareness is in creating an environment of zero tolerance for such crimes, it is equally important that punishment and accountability are inevitable. If someone takes as much bribe as he wants, if no one calls his cat "pisht", if he is not punished, children and people will have the wrong idea: "There is no justice, it is useless to fight against him." However, it is necessary to form a firm belief that there is a punishment for any crime, and that both the bribe-giver and the bribe-giver will be held accountable within the law. But it is impossible to suddenly get rid of bribery, which our eyes have already become "accustomed to". For this, it is necessary to develop simple and effective measures and implement them consistently. Take, for

example, the school admissions process. Parents want to send their child to a prestigious school with a well-known teacher so that their child can study well and get a decent education.

For this, he uses all his opportunities, uses his acquaintances, offers money and services. In fact, in order to solve the problem, it is possible to fully study why people seek this school and pedagogue, collect open information about them, control the situation, and organize admission to that class or school on a selective basis. Please, if you want your child to study in this class or school, let him take part in the competition, check his intellectual potential, and pass a psychological-pedagogical examination. Currently, this experience is partially implemented in the system. Basically, schools specializing in in-depth teaching of certain subjects accept students on a selective basis. The establishment of this rule requires taking measures to increase the quality of teaching in all educational institutions and classes, increasing competition between schools. Will there be transparency in the lower links as well? In order to encourage teachers in every way, they are being introduced to give them loans for buying houses and cars on preferential terms. Naturally, not all teachers deserve such an opportunity, but the most dedicated and advanced pedagogues who are masters of their work.

But at the lowest levels, are they impartially selected, are benefits distributed fairly? Corruption is allowed in this place too, and the lists are not compiled in a narrow framework within the interests of certain individuals? In my opinion, such a mechanism should be developed in which the human factor is minimally involved, in which the teacher's work experience, achievements and results, initiative, activity, in a word, if he is worthy in all respects, should be calculated using computer technologies on the basis of a special algorithm. Public participation should also be ensured when entering data into the system. For example, the teacher's rating at the school includes, in addition to traditional criteria such as the mastery of students, the results achieved by him and his students in various contests and competitions, the use of new educational technologies in his work, the opinions and activities of parents and students, the pedagogical team, community structures, and his former students. conclusions (accomplishments, results, descriptions) from further stages of education or from the workplace may also be taken into account. Behaviors that may harm the teacher's reputation should have a negative impact on the results of the rating. Let him understand that every wrongdoing will prevent him from getting benefits in the future. It is also possible to implement the interviewing method used by various international organizations in the fight against corruption in education. Admittedly, looking at paperwork and various reports does not fully depict the corrupt landscape. Some corrupt officials carry out all paperwork to such an extent that it is difficult to prove on the basis of papers that they have bribed, embezzled funds and looted state property.

Without evidence, it is impossible to punish the guilty. At such a time, it is convenient to conduct separate interviews with pedagogues, students, and educational officials. In one-on-one interviews, information is collected about the form of corruption, the mechanism of operation, the rings in implementation - persons, methods and tools. After that, comprehensive measures will be developed against the causes of corruption, not the corruptor. In this case, the corrupt person and those mediating him may be severely warned, the incomes, property, and expenses of officials, close relatives will be investigated, and if the illegally obtained income is found, they may be held accountable. This method makes it possible to systematically eliminate the factors that serve corruption, in which places corruption is allowed more often, and to determine the reasons for this. Anti-corruption lessons should be organized in schools in order to instill intolerance against corruption from childhood.

In the lesson, what is corruption, what are its harms can be explained in a simple language that children can understand, conversations about corruption can be held with students, and role-playing games can be played. Specific examples of corruption situations are given in the lessons, its consequences, methods of combating it, and the personal participation of the student in this. For example, everyone knows the case of getting a certain medical certificate without passing the examination and getting the job done in return for a bribe. But what happens if a person with tuberculosis who receives a medical certificate in this way works in a school cafeteria?

It is said that many people will get sick as a result, and you may be among them. Role-playing games are useful when working with young children. A situation is staged, and the role of bribe-taking industry officials is divided among the children. Or children describe their views of a conscientious and dishonest leader through pictures. The fight against bribery in society involves extensive and complex work. This disease cannot be eradicated by fighting only one cause. All causes should be thoroughly investigated, bribery, that is, not the result, but the ways leading to it, the reasons that give rise to it should be eliminated. The teacher cannot take bribes, the school director treats everyone as equal, he never abuses his position and authority, we do not pay bribes, education must have equality, legality, openness and transparency. lives side by side with us. In conclusion, today we are all equally responsible for the development of the country. Only if every individual, citizen or young adult fulfills his role in the society diligently and approaches it honestly, fully feels his duties and responsibilities, understands his obligation to the coming generation, we will achieve our highest goal of building an "enlightened society" in New Uzbekistan. I think we will be.

REFERENCES:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "Strategy of New Uzbekistan" - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2022
2. T.T. Madumarov's scientific article on the topic "Fighting corruption in the education system is a question of today's effectiveness." 16.08.2021
3. Ismailov B.I. State practice in the fight against corruption and the system of international standards // Study guide. - T.: Academy of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Scientific and educational center for combating corruption, YUMOM. 2019
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 03.01.2017 "On Combating Corruption" No. ORQ-419//[Electronic source]. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/3088008>